

Association of p and x In Quantum Mechanics

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We argue that the association of p with x arises from special relativity. In particular, if one has a rest mass, m_0 , for a particle at rest, time flows (so to speak as one continuously measures that m_0 exists) while $p=0$, $v=0$ means that the particle does not flow in x. Now m_0 , $p=0$ are the variables which Lorentz transform to E, p so we use these. In other words, we associate a flow in time with the variable E and a flow in space (x) with the variable p. We suggest that this association also holds for a photon, even though it has no rest mass.

We next consider the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction from an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. In such a case, E is the same for n_1 and n_2 and so we argue that one cannot distinguish dt in the n_1 region from dt in the n_2 region. In other words, we partially quantify the loose association between E, t into $dt = G(E)$ where G is an unknown function.

Next, we consider: $dx_1 = c_1 dt$ and $dx_2 = c_2 dt$. This implies that dx_1 and dx_2 differ, in particular due to the values of c_1 and c_2 . We suggest that dx_1 be linked to a function of p_1 and dx_2 to a function of p_2 . This then leads to $dx = \text{constant}/p$. The equation $dx_1 = c_1 dt$ with $dx_1 = \text{constant}/p$ implies that $dt = \text{constant}/E$ and so there is consistency in the definitions. We argue that dt is the same in all E regions and so it should be a function of E. In other words, there are spacetime issues linked to special relativity which apply to even probabilistic events which involve motion in spacetime, such as one dimensional reflection-refraction.

Next, we consider the n_1 - n_2 junction at $x=0$. If one considers a function of x, $F(x)$, then $dx_2 = \text{constant}/p_2$ and $dx_1 = \text{constant}/p_1$ which leads one to consider the function $F(px)$ so that $p_1 dx_1 = p_2 dx_2$, i.e. $F(y)$, where $y=px$ does not distinguish the p's. Finally, if one wishes to have $F(px)$ and its first derivative continuous at $x=0$, one is forced to introduce a "reflected" piece, which physically exists. This leads to two spacetime continuity equations which may ultimately be combined to form $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$. In other words, quantum mechanics and this classical probability equation reflect spacetime considerations which arise from special relativity, we argue.

Association of p with x

Quantum mechanics is known for associating p with x and E with t. We suggest that the origin of this association lies in the special relativistic treatment of a particle with rest mass, m_0 . In this case, m_0 exists and so there is a running or flow of the time variable, presumably due to continuous measurements of m_0 . (In an earlier note, we considered the measurement to be of $x=0$, the position, but one may just as well measure m_0 in time.) If the particle does not move, there is no flow in x. If, however, it is seen from a frame moving with $-v$ (constant), then there are two new variables:

$$p = \frac{mv}{\sqrt{1-vv/c}} \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad E = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\sqrt{1-vv/c}} \quad ((1b))$$

E, instead of m_0 , is linked with time flow and p with motion in x. At this point, the association seems to be of a very qualitative nature. We suggest that one make this association more

quantitative by considering a physical example, namely that of one dimensional reflection-refraction. We assume that the E,t and p,x associations continue to hold for a photon.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

One dimensional reflection-refraction occurs at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction at $x=0$ such that one has $E, p_1=n_1p, c_1=c/n_1$ for the incident photon, $E, -p_1=-n_1p$ for the reflected and $E, p_2=n_2p, c_2=c/n_2$ for the refracted.

Given that the energy E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photons, we argue that E is indistinguishable in both the n_1 and n_2 regions and that the same dt should hold in both. Given that we make this argument based on E , we suggest that there should be a quantitative relation:

$$dt = G(E) \text{ where } G \text{ is an unknown function ((2)).}$$

Now given dt , one may classically define:

$$dx = c dt \text{ which implies that } dx_1 = c_1 dt \text{ and } dx_2 = c_2 dt \text{ ((3))}$$

In other words, dx_1 and dx_2 are different for regions n_1 and n_2 . If one wishes to associate this difference with the relativistic variable p , then one may argue that:

$$c_1 dt = F(p_1) \text{ and } c_2 dt = F(p_2) \text{ where } F \text{ is an unknown function ((4)) such that:}$$

$$n_2/n_1 = F(p_1)/F(p_2), \text{ but } p_1=n_1p \text{ and } p_2=n_2p \text{ so } dx = \text{constant}/p \text{ is a solution ((5))}$$

In other words, the special relativistic variables E and p actually define dt and dx intervals.

Issues of Continuity

If $dx_1 = \text{constant}/p_1$ and $dx_2 = \text{constant}/p_2$, then there are issues with defining a function along the x axis, because one does not want different dx values in this function to the right and left of $x=0$. To avoid this problem, one may define the function:

$$F(p x) \text{ where } dx = \text{constant}/p \text{ ((6))}$$

In such a case $y = p dx$ with $dx = \text{constant}/p$ allows for $|-dy| = |dy|$ at the n_1 - n_2 junction $x=0$. The next consideration is of the derivative $d/dx F(p x) = p dF/dy$ ((7)).

If one wishes to make $F(p x)$ and its first derivative continuous at $x=0$, then there is a problem. This leads to the introduction of $F(-p x)$ such that:

$$A F(p_1 x) + B F(-p_1 x) = C F(p_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((8a)) and}$$

$$A p_1 \frac{d}{dy} F(p_1 x) - p_1 B \frac{d}{dy} F(-p_1 x) = C p_2 \frac{d}{dy} F(p_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((8b))$$

In this case, $F(0)$ and $dF/dy(0)$ cancel. ((8a)) and ((8b)) may be multiplied together to yield:

$$A A p_1 F \frac{dF}{dy} - p_1 B B F \frac{dF}{dy} = C C p_2 F \frac{dF}{dy} \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((9))$$

If one chooses $A=1$, then ((8a)) and ((8b)) allow one to solve for B and C in terms of p_1 and p_2 . This leads to ((9)) written as:

$$1/c_1 = B B/c_1 + C C/c_2 \quad ((10))$$

This is in the form of a probability equation for an incident, reflected and refracted photon if $B B$ and $C C$ are interpreted as fluxes. This result, however, ultimately arose from considerations of dt being the same in n_1 and n_2 while dx_1 and dx_2 differed. This leads to equations at the A, B, C level and continuity issues which ultimately lead to ((10)) instead of ((10)) being proposed a priori. In other words, spacetime considerations of the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem seem to be key, even in a probabilistic problem, if it involves motion in spacetime.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that spacetime considerations associated with special relativity seem to be key in problems involving probability, but at the same time motion in space and time. One dimensional reflection-refraction is such a problem. There is the obvious probability statement of $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$, but this statement completely bypasses any considerations of spacetime as it stands.

We argue that if one considers a particle with rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0$, then time flows and is qualitatively associated with m_0 because one may consider repeatedly measuring the presence of m_0 in time. Viewing the particle from a frame moving with constant $-v$ introduces E and p , with E being linked to motion in time and p , in space. At this point, the associations E, t and p, x seem to be quite qualitative.

We next consider one dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction at $x=0$ and assume that E, t and p, x apply to a photon. We suggest that because E is the same in n_1 and n_2 that dt in n_1 should equal dt in n_2 . In other words, we quantify to a certain degree the relation E, t to $dt = G(E)$ where G is an unknown function. Next, we write: $dx_1 = c_1 dt$ and $dx_2 = c_2 dt$ and assume $dx_1 = F(p_1)$ and $dx_2 = F(p_2)$. This leads to $dx_1 = \text{constant}/p_1$, $dx_2 = \text{constant}/p_2$ as a solution (and also $dt = \text{constant}/E$).

Given this result, if one tries to deal with a function on the x -axis, one may write $F(px)$ so that $d(px)$ in n_1 equals $d(px)$ in n_2 . If one wishes to have a continuous function and its derivative d/dx at $x=0$, then one must introduce reflection as well, obtaining ((8a)) and ((8b)). These may be solved for B, C in terms of p_1, p_2 if $A=1$. One may then combine ((8a)) and ((8b)) into a probability equation: $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$, but the main argument we wish to present is that these probabilities depend on spacetime considerations.